

Acupressure And Art Therapy: Early Study Of Patients With Comorbid Disease

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 09, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: December 10, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Acupressure, Art Therapy, Comorbidity Disorders</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5773108</p>	<p><i>The combination of acupressure and art therapy, has the potential to reduce the symptoms of comorbid disorders, so it can be used as a potential long-term complementary therapy. This therapy is based on traditional Indonesian therapy. This study aims to determine whether acupressure and art therapy can improve symptoms in comorbid patients. The study was conducted on 30 patients with physical-mental disorders and one month of acupressure and art therapy. Analysis of study data using paired sample T-test. The results showed that the correlation value of symptoms of physical and mental disorders between before and after therapy has a probability of 0.874 and 0.891 (<0.05), which means that the correlation of symptoms of physical-mental disorders before and after therapy is strong. The t-test values for physical and mental symptoms were -10,722 and -11,259 (sig 0.000), which means that acupressure and art therapy had an effect on reducing the patient's physical-mental symptoms. The results showed that acupressure and art therapy were effective and had the potential to reduce the symptoms of comorbid disorders which could also be applied to complement therapy and were also safer due to their nature.</i></p>

Introduction

Many sufferers of chronic (chronic) and recurring physical illnesses, cause / occur comorbidities (21-29%) with mental disorders, such as Migraine, Cephalgia, Asthma Bronchiale, Angina Pectoris, Gastritis, Body Pain which is chronic-exacerbation. Modern medical treatments often fail to provide permanent relief (50% - 75%). Acupressure is designed as a complementary medicine to help heal ailments (Soler et al, 2005).

Acupressure takes many forms, and in Indonesia there are several names such as "scraping" which means rubbing. The therapeutic method used is to rub certain areas repeatedly to stimulate acupuncture points and maintain energy balance. Therapy is usually used when sick or if milk production decreases (Sudjiwanati et al, 2015). Acupressure therapy is easy, inexpensive, safe from side effects, natural, and independent. Hospital paramedics, nurses, kindergarten teachers, psychology students or anyone or any interest group can practice this therapy. This therapy has no side effects, because there is no invasion, no chemicals and is related to the regeneration of several organs (through stem cells) which greatly supports the process of preventing or healing various disorders or diseases, especially those classified as comorbidities, through meridian and point therapytrigger (Chen et al, 1999). Several biomedical pathophysiology studies have found that stem cell stimulation occurs when in certain areas of the human body the manipulation is adequately synchronized with other meridian therapies such as trigger point manipulation and acupuncture therapy (Yicheng et al, 2002).

Art Therapy, is a psychotherapy that uses art as the main means of communication. Art Therapy aims to understand the psychological aspects of the patient and the healing power through a process of artistic creativity. Processes of artistic creativity can help reduce stress and symptoms, relieve traumatic experiences, and enjoy artistic experiences (Morrison, 2017).

Today, both modern medicine and alternative medicine have sought holistic healing methods. Combined treatment method is an attempt to get a better cure rate of a disease (Tabish, 2008). Acupressure therapy combined with art therapy is expected to affect the improvement of the health of patients with comorbid disorders .

Method

In this study, a sample of 30 people with medical records experienced disorders such as high blood pressure, headaches (cephalgia), vertigo, gastritis, back pain, allergies (hypersensitivity), and hyperesthesia. The patient was given a questionnaire before and after his physical impairment and psychological tests. The patient had received acupressure therapy for one month (three times / day) and art therapy four times. The results were statistically analyzed using the paired sample T-test method.

Acupressure therapy is stimulated by massaging or rubbing vertically or horizontally on the area around the acupressure point for 10-15 minutes with an intensity of three times / day which is done with acupressure. Acupuncture points used for therapy in the study included SP-6 points; ST-36; and PC-6.

The patient's psychological condition has been improved with art therapy. The art therapy method that has been given to patients is by coloring pictures. The psychological condition of the patient who is experiencing changes is identified through a graphic test. The interpretation of the graphical test results has been carried out using the data triangulation method.

Ethical approval was obtained from the Medical Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Medicine, Brawijaya University Malang, Indonesia.

Result

Based on the results of statistical calculations using the paired sample t-test, it was found that the correlation value of comorbid disorders between before and after acupressure therapy and art therapy had a probability of 0.874 and 0.891 (<0.05). These results mean a strong correlation of symptoms of comorbid disorders before and after acupressure and art therapy. The t-test values for physical and mental symptoms were -10,722 and -11,259 (sig 0.000), which means that acupressure and art therapy had an effect on reducing the patient's symptoms of physical-mental disorders.

Discussion

The results showed that acupressure and art therapy given to patients gave positive results marked by a reduction in the symptoms of physical and mental disorders experienced. The relieved symptoms of the patient's comorbid disorders can be attributed to acupressure and art therapy (18,19). Acupressure administered at ST-36, SP-6 and PC-6 points provides nerve stimulation and is known to convert amygdala-specific brain tissue towards a functional state of underlying pain perception and pain modulation (20,21). Functional connectivity as well as electrophysiological / neuroanatomic findings suggest that the efferent amygdala is associated with the anterior singular cortex, with a major role, autonomic and emotional regulation (Owens et al, 2017).

Like acupressure, art therapy works in the same way by stimulating the brain. Art therapy is believed to be able to rebalance brain function that has changed due to trauma and other emotional disorders (Bednash, 2016). The product of art therapy is made to provide stimulation to the brain through the tactile-haptic, visual sensors and perceptual channels which will be processed through the cognitive and verbal channels (Lusebrink, 2004). Through this neurological process, art as therapy is aimed at providing relaxation and directing the minds of patients experiencing anxiety, depression, and psychological trauma (Maher, 2003).

The results of a study conducted by Zick et al., Showed that relaxation acupressure therapy can improve symptoms of anxiety and at the same time reduce pain in breast cancer sufferers (Zick et al, 2018). Another study conducted by Hopton et al., Regarding comorbid disorders (depression and pain) showed that the results of the treatment given were poor but the acupuncture group was better than the other treatment group (Hopton et al, 2014). Several studies have shown that acupressure, which has superior dimensions in the form of holistic therapy, can function as adjunctive therapy, substitution therapy, complementary therapy, and may even become a replacement therapy (Walker et al, 2019).

What about art therapy? Several studies have revealed the effectiveness of art therapy for mental health disorders. Art therapy has a positive impact on people with mental disorders and its therapeutic properties are undeniable (Teglbjaerg, 2019). Accessible creative solutions to mental disorders are an essential component of an effective intervention program. Awareness of art therapy and its potential benefits remains relatively low among policymakers, the public, and those providing services. While traditional forms of Freudian art-based therapy tend to be shrouded in mystique and are considered a preservation for those with specialist training in their fields, socially oriented arts for wellness projects are much more accessible and versatile (Heenan, 2006). The positive experiences of the therapy provided help patients receive complementary therapies and other integrative therapies (Walker et al, 2019).

Acupressure and art therapy in this study can give good results in reducing the symptoms of comorbid disorders. A limitation in the research conducted was studying the symptoms felt by the participants. Further research is needed to find out how effective acupressure and art therapy are through laboratory research.

Conclusion

Acupressure and art therapy, which are traditional and holistic methods of treatment, can effectively and potentially reduce the symptoms / complaints of accompanying physical-mental illnesses and at the same time can be easily applied both individually and in ways. Acupressure and art therapy are also safe methods of treatment due to their nature and non-invasive properties. These findings warrant further evaluation in appropriate randomized controlled trials.

Statement of Ethics

This study has received ethical approval from the Medical Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Medicine, Brawijaya University Malang, Indonesia.

In s closure Statement

The author (s) of this publication has research support from the Indonesian Ministry of Research and Technology. The terms of this arrangement have been reviewed and approved by the Indonesian Ministry of Research and Technology following its policy on objectivity in research.

Funding Source

This research was funded by the DRPM Research Grant from the Indonesian Ministry of Research and Technology for the fiscal year 2017, with the contract number: 057/071028/05 / IV / 2017, dated April, 2017.

Author Contributions

All authors contribute to building ideas, developing theories, verifying methods used, processing data, discussing research results and contributing to making final manuscripts.

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